

Terpenoids and Related Compounds : XVII¹. Conversion of Crategolic Acid to Olean-12-en-2 α ,3 β -diol.

P. Sengupta and P. B. Das

Crategolic (Maslinic) acid (Ia) has been converted to olean-12-en-2 α ,3 β -diacetoxy-28-al (Ie) by Rosenmund reduction of the acid chloride (Id) and by reductive desulphurisation of the benzylthiol ester (Ih). The aldehyde (Ie) has been reduced by Huang-Minlon's method to the hitherto unknown olean-12-en-2 α , 3 β -diol (If).

As a general rule a 3-oxygen function is ubiquitous in the natural tetra and pentacyclic triterpenoids with only a few exceptions. In dioxygenated triterpenoids the second point of oxygenation is usually not at C₂. Thus although 2,3-dihydroxy functions are encountered in a large number of triterpenoids having additional oxygen functions at other positions of the carbon skeleton, the occurrence of simple triterpenoid 2,3-diols as such is rare. It is only very recently that such simple 2,3-diols belonging to hopane and modified hopane skeleton and modified oleanane skeleton have been encountered in nature^{2,3}. McGinnis and coworkers⁴ reported the preparation of the four stereoisomers of lupan-2,3-diol, although none of them have so far been found in nature. More recently Samson and coworkers⁵ have described the preparation of three out of the four stereoisomers of D : A-friedo-olean-2,3-diol, of which only the 2 α , 3 β -isomer pachysandiol-A has been isolated from nature^{5,3}.

As all the four stereoisomers of olean-12-en-2,3-diol are still unknown we became interested in their preparation. The present communication deals with the preparation of olean-12-en-2 α , 3 β -diol (If). In a previous paper⁶ we reported the isolation of oleanolic acid, ursolic acid and crategolic acid (Ia) as their respective methyl esters from the flowers of *Eugenia jambolana* Lam. Methyl crategolate (Ib) on hydrolysis by refluxing with KOH in ethylene glycol furnished crategolic acid (Ia). Now we have found that the crude free acid mixture of the flowers could be resolved into the three pure acids by silica gel chromatography. Since the two hydroxyl groups of crategolic acid (Ia) are known to be

1. Part XVI. P. Sengupta, A. K. Dey, J. Mukherjee, S. Ghosh and K. G. Das, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1969, **46**, 775.
2. (a) S. Nakamura, T. Yamada, H. Wada, Y. Inoue, T. Goto and Y. Hirata, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1965, 2017.
(b) H. Wada, G. Goto, T. Goto and Y. Hirata, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1966, 3461.
3. T. Kikuchi and T. Toyoda, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1967, 3181.
4. E. L. McGinnis, G. D. Meakins, J. E. Price and M. C. Styles, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1965, 4379.
5. A. S. Samson, S. J. Stevenson and R. Stevenson, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, C2342.
6. P. Sengupta and P. B. Das, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1965, **42**, 539.

trans-diequatorial^{7,8} we intended to utilise this acid for the preparation of olea-12-en-2 α , 3 β -diol (If) with definite configuration of the two hydroxyl groups.

We converted crategolic acid (Ia) to 2 α , 3 β -diacetoxy-olea-12-en-28-al (Ie) through two different routes. In the first route, crategolic acid diacetate (Ic) was converted into the corresponding acid chloride (Id) by treatment with thionyl chloride. The latter on Rosenmund reduction in xylene solution gave a crystalline solid, m.p. 207–212°, $[\alpha]_D + 21.05^\circ$, in

I a,	$R_1 = R_2 = H$;	$R_3 = COOH$
b,	$R_1 = R_2 = H$;	$R_3 = COOMe$
c,	$R_1 = R_2 = Ac$;	$R_3 = COOH$
d,	$R_1 = R_2 = Ac$;	$R_3 = COCl$
e,	$R_1 = R_2 = Ac$;	$R_3 = CHO$
f,	$R_1 = R_2 = H$;	$R_3 = CH_3$
g,	$R_1 = R_2 = Ac$;	$R_3 = CH_3$
h,	$R_1 = R_2 = Ac$;	$R_3 = COSCH_2.C_6H_5$

85–90% yield. That it was the desired aldehyde (Ie) was proved by its IR spectrum that showed bands at 2705 (aldehyde), 1245 and 1255 (acetate), 1740 (aldehyde and acetate) and 820 cm^{-1} (trisubstituted double bond) and its NMR spectrum (Fig. 1) that showed singlets at

Fig. 1

- L. Caglioti and G. Cainelli, *Tetrahedron*, 1962, **18**, 1061.
- R. Tschescho, E. Henckel and G. Snatzke. (a) *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1963, 613; (b) *Liebigs Ann.*, 1964, **676**, 175.

δ 0.78, 0.89, 1.07 and 1.15 ppm corresponding to 7-tertiary methyl groups, singlets at δ 1.95 and 2.05 ppm corresponding to the two acetate methyl groups, a one proton doublet centered around δ 4.7 ppm ($J = 10$ cps) due to the axial hydrogen at C_3 coupled with the axial hydrogen at C_2 , a one proton unresolved multiplet centered around δ 5.1 ppm due to the axial hydrogen at C_2 coupled with the protons at C_1 and C_3 , a one proton multiplet centered around δ 5.3 ppm due to the vinyl hydrogen at C_{12} and finally a one proton singlet at δ 9.57 ppm due to the aldehydic proton at C_{28} . The aldehyde (Ie) on oxidation with Tollen's reagent regenerated the starting diacetoxy acid (Ic). In the other route, the reductive desulphurisation of the benzylthiol ester of cratogenic acid diacetate (Ih) by Raney nickel following the method of Levin and coworkers⁹ was explored. However, the reported condition when applied for the preparation¹⁰ of the thiolester (Ih) from the diacetoxy acid chloride (Id) did not meet with success, presumably owing to the highly hindered nature of the C_{28} carbonyl function. Nevertheless, success was achieved when more drastic condition was used. Thus, when a solution of the acid chloride (Id) and benzylthiol in benzene and pyridine was heated in a sealed tube at 100° for 96 hrs. the desired thiol ester (Ih), m.p. 198–205°, $[\alpha]_D + 45.25^\circ$, was obtained in 90% yield. The IR spectrum of the compound showed peaks at 1740 and 1250 (acetate), 1670 and 708 (thiol ester¹¹) and 808 cm^{-1} (trisubstituted double bond). The thiol ester (Ih) in acetone solution was smoothly desulphurised⁹ with deactivated Raney nickel to yield the desired aldehyde (Ie).

The aldehyde (Ie) on Huang-Minlon reduction furnished olean-12-en-2 α , 3 β -diol (If), m.p. 198–203°, $[\alpha]_D + 79.9^\circ$, which did not show any carbonyl band in the IR spectra but showed only a band at 3552 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl). On acetylation it yielded 2 α , 3 β -diacetoxy-olean-12-ene (Ig), m.p. 179–181°, $[\alpha]_D + 35.46^\circ$, that did not show any hydroxyl band in the IR spectra but showed bands at 1735 and 1251 cm^{-1} (acetate).

EXPERIMENTAL

All m.ps. are uncorrected. Pet ether used had b.p. 60–80°. Optical rotations were measured in CHCl_3 .

Hydrolysis of Methyl Cratogolate (Ib) : Cratogenic Acid (Ia) : Methyl cratogolate⁶, m.p. 220–222° (1.5 g.) was refluxed with KOH (30 g.) in diethylene glycol (150 ml.) for 20 hr. Usual work up furnished a slightly coloured acid (1.4 g.), which after treatment with activated charcoal in MeOH gave (Ia), m.p. 264–268°. (Lit.¹² m.p. 267–269°).

Silica Gel Chromatography of the Acidic Components of R. jambolana Lam : Isolation of Cratogenic Acid (Ia) : The crude benzene extract⁶ from the flowers of *E. jambolana* (1 Kg) was separated into acidic and neutral fractions. The acidic matter (16 g.) was taken up in benzene and adsorbed on a column of silica gel (250 g.). Elution with benzene and benzene :

9. G. B. Spero, A. V. McIntosh, Jr. and R. H. Levin, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 1907.
10. R. H. Levin, A. V. McIntosh, Jr., G. B. Spero, D. E. Rayman and E. M. Meinzer, *ibid.*, 1948, **70**, 511.
11. L. J. Bellamy, 'The Infra-red Spectra of Complex Molecules', 1960, Methuen, London, p. 188 and 353.
12. L. Caglioti, G. Cainelli and F. Minutilli, *Gazz. Chim. Ital.*, 1961, **91**, 1387.

ether (9 : 1) removed gum, while benzene : ether (1 : 1) removed oleanolic and ursolic acids. Further elution with benzene : ether (3 : 7 and 1 : 4) furnished a solid, m.p. 260–268°, which on crystallisation from MeOH afforded pure crategolic acid (1.5 g.), m.p. 265–268°.

Crategolic Acid Diacetate (Ic) : Crategolic acid (1.6 g.) was refluxed with pyridine (16 ml.) and Ac₂O (32 ml.) for 1 hr. Usual work up resulted in a crude solid, m.p. 190–225°, which on chromatography over silica gel (15 g.) in benzene, elution with benzene : ether (9 : 1) and crystallisation from MeOH furnished (Ic), m.p. 234–236°. (Lit.¹² m.p. 235–239°).

Acid Chloride of Crategolic Acid Diacetate (Id) : The diacetate (Ic, 0.8 g.) was refluxed in dry benzene (10 ml.) with purified¹³ SOCl₂ (2 ml.) for 1 hr. Excess reagents were removed under reduced press and the residue kept in a vac. dessicator over KOH for 18 hr. The acid chloride (Id), m.p. 195–205°, was hygroscopic.

Rosenmund Reduction of Diacetoxy Crategolic Acid Chloride (Id) : 2 α , 3 β -Diacetoxy-olean-12-en-28-al (Ie) : In a three-necked round bottom flask equipped with a mercury-sealed stirrer, a reflux condenser attached to a HCl absorption device and a gas inlet system with dropping funnel was taken Pd-BaSO₄ (5%, 0.6 g.)¹⁴ in dry xylene (10 ml) and benzene (5 ml.). 10 ml of the solvent was distilled off in a current of dry H₂ under suction to ensure complete removal of moisture. The acid chloride (Id) in dry xylene (10 ml) was added to the vigorously stirred refluxing catalyst all at a time while a strong stream of dry H₂ was passed through it, until the evolution of HCl, as determined by titration from time to time, ceased (4 hr.). The catalyst was filtered off and the filtrate was evaporated in vac. The resulting solid was taken up in ether and the ether solution washed with 3% cold NaOH aq. and water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and evaporated to yield a neutral solid (0.56 g.) which was chromatographed over neutral alumina (15 g.). Elution with pet ether : benzene (4 : 1) afforded a crystalline solid (0.54 g.), m.p. 190–205°, which on crystallisation from acetone-MeOH gave pure Ie (as plates), m.p. 207–212°, [α]_D+21.05°. (Found : C, 75.36; H, 9.44. C₃₄H₅₂O₅ requires : C, 75.51; H, 9.69%). IR (see Theoretical). NMR (See Fig. 1).

Oxidation of the Aldehyde (Ie) to the Diacetate Acid (Ic) with Tollen's Reagent : The diacetoxy aldehyde (Ie, 0.1 g.) in MeOH (10 ml.) was treated in the cold with 10 ml. of Tollen's reagent¹⁵ for 6 hr. and subsequently the mixture was heated at 40° for 2 hr., when a silver mirror formed. Usual work up furnished a solid (0.08 g.), which on crystallisation from ether : pet ether was found to be identical with authentic Ic.

Benzylthiol Ester of Crategolic Acid Diacetate (Ih) : The acid chloride (Id, 0.35 g.) in dry benzene (10 ml.) and pyridine (10 ml.) was heated in a sealed tube at 100° with benzylthiol¹⁶ (freshly distilled over P₂O₅) for 96 hr. Solvent and excess benzylthiol were removed under reduced press, and the residue taken up in ether. The ether soln. was washed with 1% HCl aq. water, 1% NaOH aq. and water, dried (Na₂SO₄) and evaporated to yield a

13. A. I. Vogel, *A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry*, 1959, Longmans, London, p. 189.

14. Ref. 13, p. 951.

15. Ref. 13, p. 330.

16. R. L. Frank and P. V. Smith, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 2103.

gummy solid (0.34 g.), which on crystallisation from MeOH furnished pure Ih (0.26 g.), m.p. 198–205°, $[\alpha]_D + 45.25^\circ$. (Found : C, 74.49; H, 8.59; S, 4.99. $C_{41}H_{88}O_4S$ requires : C, 74.28; H, 8.82; S, 4.83%). IR (See Theoretical).

Desulphurisation of Ih with Raney Ni : 2α , 3β -Diacetoxyolean-12-en-28-ol (Ie) : Raney Ni¹⁷ (1.8 g.), was refluxed with acetone (3.6 ml.) for 1 hr., the thiolester (Ih, 0.18 g.) in acetone was added and the mixture again refluxed for 1 hr. The catalyst was filtered off and the filtrate concentrated to a small volume. After usual work up⁹, the product (0.16 g.) was chromatographed over neutral alumina (5 g.). Pet ether : benzene (4 : 1) eluted a solid, which on crystallisation from acetone-MeOH furnished pure Ie, m.p. 195–198°, identical (mixed m.p. and IR) with the diacetoxy aldehyde (Ie), obtained from Rosenmund reduction.

Olean-12-en-2 α , 3 β -diol (If) : The diacetoxy aldehyde (Ie, 0.38 g.) in EtOH (5 ml.) and diethylene glycol (40 ml.) was refluxed with 80% hydrazine hydrate (4.5 ml.) for 1.5 hr., powdered KOH (0.38 g.) was added and the mixture further refluxed for 1 hr. The condenser was removed and the mixture again heated until the inner temp. was 210°. A dry condenser was fitted and the reactants again refluxed for 2.5 hr. After usual work up a semi-solid mass (0.38 g.) was obtained. It was chromatographed over alumina (10 g.). Elution with benzene : ether (4 : 1) gave a solid (0.3 g.), which on crystallisation from $CHCl_3$ -MeOH afforded the pure diol (If) as needles, m.p. 198–203°, $[\alpha]_D + 79.9^\circ$. (Found : C, 81.39; H, 11.18. $C_{30}H_{50}O_2$ requires : C, 81.39; H, 11.38%). IR (See Theoretical).

2α , 3β -Diacetoxyolean-12-ene (Ig) : The above diol (If, 0.15 g.) was acetylated in the usual manner with Ac_2O (3 ml.) and pyridine (1.5 ml.). The crude product (0.15 g.) on crystallisation from acetone-MeOH furnished pure Ig (0.09 g.), m.p. 179–181°, $[\alpha]_D + 35.46^\circ$. (Found : C, 77.41; H, 10.09. $C_{34}H_{54}O_4$ requires : C, 77.52; H, 10.33%). IR (See Theoretical).

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Organic Chemistry Laboratory,
University of Kalyani,
Nadia, West Bengal.

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17. Ref. 13, p. 871.